

REGULATING PRIVATE CONDUCT THROUGH INSTITUTION OF HISBA: RELEVANCE TO JOLO LOCAL GOVERNANCE

Anthony R. Abdulla, MAIS

Department of Islamic Studies, Sulu State College, Jolo, Sulu

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17621904>

ABSTRACT

This study, originally undertaken as master's thesis in 2019 explores that the transaction in town of Jolo involved unethical behaviors because the areas of regulating private conduct in business are not observed such as Usury, Pagsanda Tiyanum, Double price and fraud in business. Because the higher offices like the municipal government are not concerned in the implementation of regulatory law's - besides, the implementing agency like the DTI does not execute their mandates power to control the price of prime commodities for daily human consumption. In order to promote peace and order through institutionalization of Hisba, the regulatory laws are needed, and the DTI should perform its mandate as provided by the law in order to have effective peace and order in the town of Jolo. To institutionalize the private conduct in Jolo, education should come first. In every barangay education should be strengthened in order the people understand the business ethics in line with teaching of Islam. And besides, people should also be enlightened with the fear of Allah because the fear of Allah is the root of all faith. and also, local legislator should strengthen the enforcement of policy to regulate the private conduct of the people in the town of Jolo through monitoring to promote personal awareness in all business and other personal transaction.

Keywords: *Regulating private conduct, Unethical behaviours, Institutionalization of Hisba.*

INTRODUCTION

Jolo is the Capital town of Sulu with a population of around 100,000 who are mostly Muslims. It is facing with different problem from lack of water. supply, power storage population congestion that causes traffic, urban poor, rising poverty incidence, lack of school facilities and poor delivery of basic services to the people. These problems actually contribute to the deterioration of peace and order. This deplorable situation projects the true state of Jolo local governance. This is one factor that discourages inventors to participate in the local development process. The present business practice and social in Jolo are largely not conforming to the principle of Shariah. And the whole problem should be viewed as systematic in the sense that economic and social should not be tackled in isolation from the political system from this perspective, the political system of Jolo requires a fundamental mental reform - the integration of the institution of Hisba as the lead agency to speed up the regulation of the private conduct.

Any political system is ought to discharge an administrative function consisting of 1.) Regulation of private conduct, 2.) Government exaction, 3.) Disbursement of money and commodities, and 4.) Direct provisions of goods and services upon the people. The first function is undoubtedly not carried out in proper way. for Instance, the lack of order in turn open the rise of anarchy Institutionalized of Hisba in Jolo is the proper and relevant. response to address the rising anarchy.

The necessity of Hisba in the society is enshrined in Al – Qur’an, and Sunnah of the prophet Muhammad (PPUH) in more than one place. From the Al – Qur’an:

"And let there be (arising) from you a nation inviting to (all that is) good enjoining what is right and forbidding what is wrong. And those will be successful" (Al-Qur’an, 3: 104)

From the hadith, Prophet Mohammad (PBUH) decrees that: " whoever among yon sees an evil action, let him change it with his hand (by taking action); and if he cannot, then with his tongue (by speaking out); and if he cannot, then with his heart (by hating it and feeling it is wrong), and that is the weakest faith" (Sahih Al - Muslim; 78).

Also establishing an institution like hisba is a cause and sign of successful leadership Al-Qur’an decrees:

"Verily, Allah will help those who help His (Cause). truly, Allah is All - Strong, All mighty. Those (Muslim ruler's) who, if we give them power in the land, (they) enjoin prayers to pay zakat and they enjoin all - ma'ruf (i - e all that Islam orders one to do) forbid Al-munkar (all that Islam has forbidden). And with Allah rests the end of (all) matters " (Al – Qur’an 22: 40 - 41).

The purpose of this study is to institutionalize of hisba in ensuring ethical business practice in the locality. The aim in to correct the erroneous impression that the institution is meant only to serve spiritual and social purpose in the society devoid of economic contribution. (Attahiru, 2016)

Research Questions

One of the administrative functions of the local government is to regulate the private conduct specially in business activities in order to protect the public from fraud, deception and all forms of business by unscrupulous people. Without effective regulation of the private conduct as what happened to day in Sulu, business fraud, side walk vendors and the sale of unlawful products spread. The absence of regulation, business establishment like restaurant and coffee shops cannot be motivated to improve and maintain good service from sanitation to the handling of foods, business establishment continues to open their operation even it is on Friday. It is through regulation by which the government can establish effective order in the society. Qur-an basis of regulating the private conduct, is the ayah on inviting what is right, enjoining what is good and forbidding what is wrong, it is therefore imperative to raise.

1. What are the areas of regulating private conduct as expressed in the legal system of the government and Shariah?
2. What are the factors that hinder the enforcement of regulatory Laws in Jolo?
3. How does the Jolo municipal government establish effective peace and order through institutionalization of hisba?

METHODOLOGY

This study used descriptive method. Descriptive method is a scientific method which involves observing and describing the characteristics of the subject. It involves the description, recording, analysis, and interpretation of the present nature, composition or process of phenomena. The focus is on prevailing condition of relationship that exists, practices that prevail, belief, processes that are being felt or trends that are developing. It is often combined with comparison and contrast involving measurement, classification, interpretation, and evaluation. The research instrument used in this study are focus group discussion or FGD, questionnaire, focus question, interview guide and community observation. Six participants in the FGD were selected: Ulama, Kaguruhan and academicians. Library work was also undertaken.

RESULTS

The focus Group discussion (FGD) revealed a strong consensus among participants on regulating private conduct through institution of Hisba in ensuring ethical business in Jolo. The discussion yielded the following key findings:

Areas of Regulating Private Conduct

This deals with the individual actions/behavior of a person who are engaging in the following transaction or engagement like. Usury, selling, pagsanda, tyanum and double

price services. It also involved business practices like fraud, established pawnshop and as well as deception.

Riba (Usury)

Riba refers to any illegal income which includes usury bribery, profiteering, business fraud and exploitation of the masses through force and state policies. In Sulu the practice of riba spread for and wide.

Practice of Pagsanda tiyanum

Pagsanda tiyanum is one of the adat or traditions existing in Jolo particularly in some rural areas in the province. They engaged on this transaction for some reasons such as schooling, hospitalization, wedding and any related to that. They pawned their land. But instead to lessen their burden it can give another problem.

Double Price in Business

Double price is a situation in which some products or service is sold at different prices in different markets. There are a number of reasons why dual pricing may be employed, including the following an aggressive competition may occur to double pricing to drastically lower its price in a new market.

Frauds in Business

Any business deal that involves injustice or cheating or exploitation is prohibited and cancellable by the Islamic law even after it is concluded. On the other hand, cheating, hiding defects of merchandise from the dealers, exploiting the needs of customers monopoly of stocks to force one's own prices are still sinful acts and punishable by Islamic Law.

DISCUSSION

Effective Jolo governance has always been the vision and aspiration of the people of Sulu. To make it effective and responsive, the leaders and others stakeholders should start and concentrate on the regulating private conduct through the nationalization of hisba in accordance with the injunctions of the Shariah and local governance code.

Good Governance refers to the upholding of the policy of transparency, accountability, and wider participation of the people in decision- making process. (Bara, 2013)

Failure of Good Governance will result in the spread of poverty. Michael P. Todaro defines absolute poverty as a situation where a population or section of population is able to meet only its bare subsistence essentials of food, clothing, and shelter to maintain minimum levels of living absolute poverty is meant to represent. a specific minimum level of income, to satisfy the basic physical needs of food, clothing, and shelter in order to ensure

continued survival. The extend of poverty in any country depend on two factors.: The average level of income and the degree of inequality in its distribution. (Todaro, 1997).

Islamic state is an indispensable entity for the implementation of Shariah. Muslim nation cannot be called Islamic State unless it follows Shariah as its fundamental law of the land. Under Islamic state, the highest chief executive does not act as the sovereign leader, he is just a khalifa whose duty is to implement and guard the interest of shariah. The very nature of Shariah is to regulate such as the enforcement of its criminal laws, economic, political, and others necessitates the establishment of Islamic State. (Bara, 2007).

In the Islamic state, the needy have to be lent money on no interest, for this leads to affection and ensures cooperation among the members of the community, both rich and poor, whereas usury arouses hostility and hatred among people. (Tabbarah, 1978).

An Islamic State must bring all productive resources into use, including unemployed manpower, unused land, water resources and minerals. An Islamic State must take steps to root out corruption and all harmful pursuits even if they are economically lucrative. Individual freedom may have to be sacrificed for the social good. (Sarwar, 1984).

Regulating Private Conduct

Regulating private conduct refers to adoption of measures aimed at preventing peoples from unethical behavior in the conduct of private life, any harmful effects of business fraud environmental destruction, pollution, terrorism, etc.

Riba (Usury)

Riba (Usury) is one of the forbidden business transactions prohibited by Allah (S.W.T) through it is still prohibited, there is a lot of people engaging in this transaction for instance pawnshop, 5/6 loan shark and other close to it. Pawnshop is prevalent or very common transaction in Jolo. Jolo composed of many Tausug. Muslim and Muslim scholars who are knowledgeable about Riba. But this kind of unethical business still exist and could not stop. Perhaps for some reasons like poverty, ignorance and worst negligence of Allah's commands. Sad to say such reality is hard to stop unless the Ulama and the governance will cooperate to implement the Shariah, some of the reason why some people engaging Riba the people have no alternative because when they run to their relatives they might be rejected or have no money to borrow them so in time of necessity when they need money they would go to pawnshop or any related to that.

According to FGD, participant A, the Law for the Prohibition of riba was already stated very clearly in the Qur'an but not clear to man's Understanding because most of them were innocent or ignorant of the law in the Qur'an and well as secular laws. To him, lack of knowledge both Islamic and secular education people could not have faith because people who have faith will never engage in any act against the Qur'an and Sunnah of the Prophet. (S.A.W).

Participants B said, there are many people Understand that riba is unlawful in Islam, but most of them don't have faith and knowledge about it. There are people have faith however they never find the essence of real knowledge of Islam so that they can avoid from doing such riba, and besides, they don't think alternatives for them just to scrape away from doing it.

Likewise, Participant C has agreed to the opinion of Participants B but he still added, riba could not be stopped right away because there was no municipal or provincial ordinance to stop riba in our place, that is why riba still exists.

meanwhile, Participant D said, the reason why riba can never be stopped, first, the form of government that we have is secular government permitted business agencies to sell Haram foods or drinks. The selling of liquor and pork which are Haram in Islam. They also permitted individual or group of people to establish pawnshop though in the sight of the shariah law pawnshop is prohibited second, the Islamic principles or rules are not implemented as a system of government to control any engagement or act that are prohibited by Islamic law, except in the performance of ibadah like offering the prayer (SALAH); the giving aims (Obligation of sadaqah); performing of fast in the month of Ramadan going to Mecca for Haj, etc. He added, beside from Allah's will, government is the only factor that can control everything with due process of law.

In shariah meaning of Riba is a term that is used when two parties exchange item of same kinda and in return one party received extra (or in excess) of what he gave. A simple example is when give 100 units of gold and received 120 units of gold in return. The extra or excess 20 units are considered riba.

The most common application of riba is one monetary transaction relating to "LOANS" and credits. A simple example of loan is when lender gives \$1000 to a debtor with an agreement that debtor will return \$1200 on specified date. Hence, the lender will receive extra \$200 (either as his service free, rent income or reward for lending money for stated time period). This extra \$200 is absolute form of riba in Islamic Shariah.

Similarly, other financial transaction involving riba, such as advancing money on interest, keeping deposits in a bank for the sake of earnings interest, or getting concession in rates of goods or commodities against advance payments of price, most of gaging, and utilizing an income-yielding property against a certain a predetermined and fixed a rate of profit are all for hidden transactions because they involve riba in some form or the other and the person doing any of these transactions invariably pay X amount of money, but in return gets X+ more back (without profit and loss sharing). Islamic Shariah doesn't limit riba application to loan or financial transaction. Fact the canvas of riba is spread cross larger transaction involving any exchange for items between two parties, as far as the items are of some kind, and one item is exchange for other for either more or less. (Razi, 2008).

Types of Riba on Transaction

Majority of Fugaha (Jurists) stated two types of Riba in transaction

1. Riba on Credit

- a. (Riba of Jahiliya) It's additional interest's payment to extent the due date of payment.
- b. (Riba of an-nasiya) This is the riba on Credit transaction, when two items of same kinds are exchanged but one or both parties' delays delivery or payment.

2. Riba al-Fadl selling or exchanging same kind of items with more/less; (ex. 10 lbs gold exchanged for 12 lbs gold). The excess payment when items of same kinds are exchanged is called Riba al-Fadl the prophet (pbuh) declared that prohibited. (Razi , 2008).

PRACTICE OF PAGESANDA TIYANUM

PAGESANDA TIYANUM, is one of the adat or traditional existing in Jolo particularly in some rural areas in the province. They engaged on this transaction for some reasons such as schooling, hospitalizations, wedding and any related to that. They pawned their land, but instead to lessen their burden it can give another problem. The same is true with the PAGESANDA TIYANUM. First it is prohibited by Allah (S.W.T) - second it is complicated every problem have a solution before seeking anyone help pray first and asks Allah's help, and guidance for us not to go wrong. Strong faith is the real weapon of the believers.

According to Participant A PAGESANDA TIYANUM is adat, it creates personal problem on the part of the person who pawned his property. Islam does not permit us to do this kind of practice because there are instances that the pawned does not want to happen in case when the person who pawned his property should not redeem immediately, unless it reaches the iddah. The practice of PAGESANDA TIYANUM is a kind of help for friends and relatives not a matter of taking advantage the right of others.

Likewise, Participants B said, PAGESANDA TIYANUM is adat done with iddah. The iddah is a minimum of 6 months the pawned is allowed to redeem his own property.

Participants C on the other hand added that PAGESANDA TIYANUM is a rindao. Meaning when the pawned can recover his money, the property being pawned will be returned back to the owners right without returning the principal loan to the pawned.

The chairman of the FGD said, the way of PAGESANDA of his grandfather was different from other because he gave the money to the pawned, then he advises him to take the responsibility to work on the property to earn something from it. But the earnings from the property which the pawn receive would equal to the amount he pawned, the said property would be returned to the owner or otherwise the said be owned by pawned.

The Islamic Point of View on PAGESANDA TIYANUM

From the Shariah point of views, Pagsandah Tiyanum is not allowed but in terms of lending land for a specified period of time, a specified fee and for food is permissible as mentioned in the following hadeeth it is reported on the authority of Rafi' iba khadeej that Ansar". He further said " we used to rent land, on the agreement that a portion of the yield was for us and portion for them (land lords) and sometimes this piece of land would produce a yield while that piece would not, so the Prophet (S.A.W) forbid us from doing this. But as for (accepting) silver (as a payment for using the land) he did not forbid that" this is an authentic hadeeth.

It's is reported from the authority of Jabir Ibn Abdullah that he said, " we used to cultivate land during the life time of the messenger of Allah, and we got a share out of the grain left in the ears after harvesting them and something in specified so the messenger of Allah said " he who has land should cultivate it or let his brother till it otherwise he should leave it " This is an authentic hadeeth.

Narrated Rafi' bin Khadija, my uncle Zuhair said"Allah's messenger forbade us to do a thing which was a source of help to us " I said, " whatever Allah's messenger said was right. He spoke. "Allah's messenger sent for me and asked what are you doing with your farms? I replied we give our farms on rent on the basis that we get the yield produced at the banks of the water streams (irrigation channels) for barely and dates", Allah's messenger said, do not do so, but cultivate (the land) by your selves or let it be cultivated by other gratis or keep it cultivated, " I said, we hear and obey", (Salih Al-Bukhari, Hadith No.532, vol-3)

DOUBLE PRICE IN BUSINESS

Double price in business is a forbidden business that one should be aware of but it really existing here in Jolo. Rice for example the price gradually increasing higher than expecting price. It increased for some reasons Lock of stock bad weather and even an explainable reason so the customers suffer and it really caused a burden on their parts another sad reality is that every Ramadan there is always price like this kind of situation should give much attention for the government and should be not taken for granted, The DTI have responsibility on this matter.

Double price in business happen according to participant A said when someone took some items or good from other person to sell then that someone doesn't pay or ask the real prices of the said items or the real price has given to someone however, he will pay later after the selling. Meaning he took profits from the items then increased of payment of such item is allowed

Participant B said double price may happen when a person engages in business has Lock awareness of Islamic concept of selling Lock of awareness in the sense the person has Lock of knowledge in Islamic concept in business. Justice is needed in the daily life of

human transaction like in buying and selling of goods Islam does not permit individual to sell good which you don't have like making swan (fixing).

Double price in Islam is prohibited it is mentioned in one hadeeth narrated by Abu Hurairah (R.A) Allah's messenger for bade tow transaction combine in one in this form one price form of trade the seller fixes two prices for an article. One price for cash payment and the second price for credit purchase. The extra money added to the credit purchase is considered interest and the therefore unlawful.

ISLAMIC CONCEPT OF PRICE

Price is changeable according to the existing market reality it's regulation usually becomes controversial either from the purely analytical view point or from the Islamic point of view. In Islam the urged for the control or regulation of price should come from within the community.

the Islamic concept of price precludes of any type of exploitation either from the producer's side or the consumer side The necessity of educating people under the state patronage and control with a view to harmonizing the dictates of Islamic social justice with the demand of producer's incentive. However, to keep the level of the basic necessities of life within the reach of common an Islamic state must take a number of policy decision and resolution so that farmers get the due price of their produce. There is a need for the conduct of seminars or discussions between producers and consumers under state patronage with the clear objective of in buying them with on Islamic code of transactions and long-term measures. (Panda ,2003)

FRAUDS IN BUSINESS

Any business deal that involves injustice or cheating or exploitation is strictly prohibited and cancellable by the Islamic law even after it is concluded. On the hand, cheating, hiding defects of merchandise from the dealers, exploiting the needs of customers, monopoly of stocks to force one's own prices are all sinful acts a d punishable by the Islamic law.

Manipulation of goods is an example of fraud according to participant A advertisement is an example of Fraud according to Participant B. Selling itself, there is a concept of "hiding process" the rules that governed the hiding process are bida'a and fraud or deception, similar to the process of double price in business according to Participant C.

DECEPTION IN BUSINESS

Deception in business engaged by some traders in Jolo like giving short measurements, cheating by hiding defects in goods and commodities, forcing someone to buy and to sell something own the sales to this brother it is Haram (prohibited) in Islam as mentioned in Hadeeth as follows:

1. The warning giving short measure or weight;

it is reported on the authority of Abdullah bin Abbas that he said: when the prophet arrived in Al- Madinah they were the worst of people for giving short measure then Allah, the Almighty, the All-powerful revealed: Woe to al-mutaffifeen (those who give less in measure and weight decrease the rights of others) [83] After that they become the best people for giving full measure! This is an authentic Hadeeth.

2. The warning against cheating and the encouragement to give advice when selling.

It is reported on the authority of Abu Hurairah that the messenger of Allah said: " He who acts dishonesty towards us is not of us. " This is an authentic hadeeth on the authority of Abu Hurairah that the Prophet happened to pass by a heap of eatables (corn). He thrust his hand in that (heap) and his fingers were moisture. He said to the owner of the eatables (corn)," what is this? " He replied on messenger of Allah! These have been soaked by rainfall. He (the Prophet asked) why did you not place this (the soaked part of the heap) over other eatables so that the people could see it? He who deceives is not of me (is not my follower). This is an authentic Hadeeth.

4. It is not permissible to sell by Al-munabazah (is to throw the roll of cloth the dark to each other and to accept whatever the catch is without saying the goods) or by Al-mulamasah (is a by for pre-fixed price with close eyes or in the darkness just by first touch of the hand)

It is reported on the authority of Abu Sa'eed Al-khudiri said: the messenger of Allah forbade us from a practicing two types of business transaction and from two ways of dressing: he forbade Al-mulamasah and Al-munabazah in transaction. Al-mulamasah. Means the touching of another garment with hand, either at night or by day without examine it except this much. Al-munabazah means that a man throws his garment to another and the other throws his garment, thus conforming their contract without inspection or mutual agreement " this is an authentic hadeeth, example of sale by Al-munabazah, two persons may agree to barter one thing for another without seeing or checking either of them one may say to another. " I barter my garment for your garment" and the sale is achieved without either of them seeing the garment of the other, or may say " I give you what I have and you give me what you have", and thus they buy from each other without knowing how much each has had.

Example of sale by Al-mulamasah, one brings a folder garment in the dark and the buyer offers a price and the owner of the garment says: I sell it to you on condition that you will only touch it, not see it and if you see it, you have no option to cancel the sale"(Bin Hassan Hallaq, 2007).

5. It is not permissible for a Muslim to sell something over the sale of his brother.

On the authority of Abu Hurairah that he said: The messenger of Allah said: "do not envy one another do not deceive one another in bidding, do not hate one another do not turn your backs on one another and do not intrude on the transactions of one another but be servant of Allah, brothers. A Muslim is the brother of a Muslim, he neither oppresses him nor abandons him, he neither lies him nor looks down on him. Righteousness is right here and he pointed to his breast three times. It is sufficient evil for a person to look down upon his brother Muslim. The whole of Muslim to another Muslim is inviolable: his blood, his property and his honor.

Deception of a buyer by offering a higher price for something on sale without the intention of buying -thus the potential buyer is forced to pay higher price than he would have done otherwise this concept of selling is called Najash. The literal meaning of "najash" is "bait" i-e that which is offered by a hunter to allure a prey, such action is prohibited whether done in conspiracy with the seller or separately, merely to harm a buyer by making him pay more than necessarily.

Intrusion on a transaction - it is meant the entrance of a third party with a better offer after an agreement has been reached between two sides over a sale, particularly concerning the price such is prohibited in Islam. (Muhammad,1999)

FACTORS HINDERING THE ENFORCEMENT OF REGULATORY

1. The higher offices are not concerned in the enforcement of regulatory laws.

One of the factors that hinder the enforcement of regulatory laws is the higher offices like municipal government are not concerned in the enforcement of regulatory laws.

According to Participant A, the higher offices are not concerned in the enforcement of regulatory laws in order to regulate the business system of the people in Jolo, and it is not in their program to implement the Shariah law in the aspect of business transaction.

The higher offices like municipal government should be concerned in the enforcement of regulatory laws and even though it is not in their program since they are Muslim, the executive office should implement the Shariah law in the aspect of business transaction. The impact of the church and the government should not be separated but to function as one body in the administration, like public policy one of dimension of public policies is regulative. It means regulating the business conduct through regulation and imposition of restrictions or limitation on the behavior of individuals and groups. In other words, the business conduct here in Jolo can regulate through regulation of Hisba institution in order to address the unethical behavior in business transaction.

The essence of administrative process is strict compliance of the law, fulfillment of public duties. Obedience to the leader and public service without observing this essence there can be no harmony in the process of administrative.

2. Shariah law is not implemented.

Shariah law is not implemented in Jolo except code of Muslim personal laws known as PD no. 1083 because the government is not an Islamic state.

Islamic state is a type of government primarily based on the application of shariah (Islamic law), dispensation of Justice and maintenance of law and order. Even though our place is not an Islamic state, it does not mean that it cannot follow Shariah in business transaction. Majority of individual who are engaging business in Jolo are Muslims, so they should adopt Islamic work ethic.

Islamic work ethic is seen as the trader's conduct based on fear to Allah which comprises justice, commitment and cooperation with a view to achieving Falah (success) it is also referred to as creative and oriented participation towards work and also as a virtue in needs of person as well as the necessity to create balance his social and individual Life and at the same time as dis charging his duties toward Allah (SWT) (Attahiru, 2016)

According to participant A although shariah has been established in Jolo but it's mandate is only relative to the person and family relations. but as far as person is concerned it cannot be avoided that private conduct is a part.

Participant B added Shariah court was already there but they did not implement because there is no power enforce to uphold or execute the Shariah law and there will be no monitoring from the higher up.

3. Negligence of DTI's duties

The department of trade and industries (DTI) is government agency mandate to monitor the price of the prime commodities in Jolo. But it is failed to observe its mandate which is one reason why private conduit is not regulate when DTI office does not observe the duties and responsibilities as one of the implementing agencies to execute regulatory laws here in Jolo the unethical behaviors in business transaction just as what happen today in market has been existing. We can see there in engaging usury, cheating, deception, and others. As for as DTI is concerned, they should perform their mandated.

The department also undertaken aggressive price monitoring and conducts regular market visits to ensure that basics and prime commodities are made available to consumers at reasonable prices according to participant A one of the implementing agencies to execute regulatory laws is the DTI. It is under their mandates to control the prices of the prime commodities if they could not afford to do, they can ask the cooperation of the other authorities like police men municipal government and as well as the provincial government to deliver their service and by educating the people about business ethics it

is because majority of our business men are lack of awareness both secular and Islamic laws.

PROMOTION OF PEACE AND ORDER THROUGH INTITUTIONALIZATION OF HISBA

To institutionalize hisba in Jolo is one way to establish peace and order because if private conduct is not regulated negative competition is common miscommunication can easily happen. Those the municipal government must be aware.

To regulate private conduct in business is necessary in order to avoid negative competition and it must be done through resolutions and massive education. A side from the sermon being delivered by the kaguruhan (preachers) during Friday congregational prayer, series of seminars and symposium must be done. In this purpose the LGU of Jolo and the DTI should coordinate with the kaguruhan.

According to participant A to regulate the private conduit of the people in business education should come first in every barangay education should be strengthened in order the people understand the business ethics in line with the teaching of Islam and besides people should also be enlightened with the fear of Allah because it is the root of all faith as far as private conduct is concerned participant B added in his opinion lamented that the local legislator should strengthen the enforcement of policy to regulate the private conduct of the people in the town of Jolo through monitoring in order to promote personal awareness in business and all other personal transactions.

Conclusions

The problem of on how to Institutionalize hisba in Jolo in reflected in research questionnaires like the case of question number one, it emphasizes the different private practices involved in business in Jolo, like riba Usury, pagsanda tiyanum and double price in a Tausug concept it is needed to be regulated by Islamic law so that legitimate business transaction will be attained.

The case of question number two, reveals the factors which hinder the enforcement of regulatory Laws, the higher officers are not concerned in the implementation of the regulatory Laws in order to regulate the business system in Jolo in accordance with the Shariah and also the implementing agency does not execute their mandates to control the price of prime commodities.

Likewise, the case of last question, reveals on how to promote peace and order through institutionalization of hisba, it emphasizes that private conduct in business must be regulated through resolutions as a guide implementing mechanics likewise, the DTI should perform it's mandates as provided by the law in over to regulate bad practices in the conduct of business in the town of Jolo in coordination the Philippine National Police so that the police power of data DTI and LGU of Jolo can be exercised.

Recommendations.

The researcher would like to recommend that to Institutionalize the private conduct business in Jolo, education should come first. In every barangay education should be strengthened in order the people can understand the business ethics in line with the teaching of Islam. And besides, people should Also be enlightened with the fear of Allah because it is the root of all faith. And also, local legislator should strengthen the enforcement of policy to regulate the private conduct of the people in the town of Jolo through monitoring in order to promote personal awareness in all business and other personal transaction.

Compliance with Ethical standards

The researcher ensured full compliance with ethical standards throughout the study by obtaining informed consent from all participants, allowing them to with draw at any time, safeguarding their anonymity and data privacy, avoiding any conflict of interest or plagiarism, and using the researcher solely for academic purposes.

Acknowledgements

The researcher wishes to acknowledge the following important people: thesis adviser Dr. Adjili N. Isduri, for continuous support and priceless advice, suggestions and recommendation in making this paper a reality, Prof Alphata J. Unti, critic and Dr. Magna Anissa A. Hayudini, a panel member for their suggestions and corrections.

The researcher also wishes to thank the chairman of the panel, Dr. Muammar S. Sakili for his Stewardship during the defense and also the following persons: Prof. Hannibal H. Bara, Ph D. Imam Al-Rashir C. Kulani, Dr. Adjili N. Isduri, Dr. Al-annawar J. Ansar, Sir Javier H. Haiber and Sir Hji.Nizam A. Alsad.

Special thanks is highly reserved for Dr. Charisma S. Ututalum, CESE, President of the Sulu State College and to Sheikh Alfadzri B. Moharrani for their moral support and encouragement.

Above all, the researcher highest thanks goes to the Almighty Allah for granting him patient strength and wisdom to finish this humble work.

REFERENCES

- Attahiru, M.S, & Al-Aidarus, A. & Md Yusop, S. (2016). Moderating Role of hisbah institution on the relationship of religiosity and Islamic culture to Islamic work ethics in Nigeria. international. Review of management and marketing, ISSN: 2146-4405.
- Bara, H. H. (2007). Guide to Islamic Administration. Waqaf foundation Inc. Jolo.
- Bara, H. H. (2013) Public Administration: A Contextual Approach, Wagaf Foundation, Inc- Jolo.

- Bin Hassan Hallaq, M. (2007). Fiqh (according to the Qur'an and Sunnah, Darussalam, Riyadh.
- Muhammad, U (1999). The forty Hadith of Al-imam An- Annawawi text with explanatory Notes, Abul-Qasim publishing house, Jeddah.
- Panda, A. B (2003). Islamic Economy: It's Relevance to the Globalization of Economy in the Muslim Filipino area Mindanao State University, Marawi City.
- Razi, M. (2008). Riba in Islam Fiqh of Contemporary Issues, Toronto Canada.
- Sarwar, G. (1984) Islam Beliefs and Teachings, The Muslim Educational Trust, London.
- Tabbarah, A. A (1978) The Spirit of Islam Doctrine and Teaching, Beirut, Lebanon.
- Todaro, M. P. (1997) Economic Development, Massachusetts, Addison-Wesley Studies.